

Routing Diagram for 25-0092 Sunny Skies Comprehensive Model w.o Upstream RC
 Prepared by Complete Design INC., Printed 4/15/2026
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25-0092 Sunny Skies Comprehensive Model w.o Upstream RO

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Pipe Listing (all nodes)

Line#	Node Number	In-Invert (feet)	Out-Invert (feet)	Length (feet)	Slope (ft/ft)	n	Diam/Width (inches)	Height (inches)	Inside-Fill (inches)
1	ST-1	1,008.20	1,005.30	31.0	0.0935	0.013	12.0	0.0	0.0
2	ST-3	1,005.30	1,004.86	21.0	0.0210	0.012	12.0	0.0	0.0
3	ST-5	996.79	995.48	65.0	0.0202	0.013	12.0	0.0	0.0
4	ST-6	995.38	994.96	20.0	0.0210	0.013	12.0	0.0	0.0
5	ST-7	994.86	994.22	64.0	0.0100	0.013	12.0	0.0	0.0
6	ST-8	997.94	993.75	93.0	0.0451	0.013	12.0	0.0	0.0
7	ST-9	993.65	991.00	80.0	0.0331	0.013	12.0	0.0	0.0

25-0092 Sunny Skies Comprehensive Model w.o UpType IA 24-hr 100-Year Rainfall=2.60"

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Time span=0.00-36.00 hrs, dt=0.10 hrs, 361 points

Runoff by SBUH method, Split Pervious/Imperv.

Reach routing by Dyn-Stor-Ind method - Pond routing by Dyn-Stor-Ind method

Subcatchment B1: BASIN 1	Runoff Area=0.158 ac 100.00% Impervious Runoff Depth=2.37" Tc=10.0 min CN=0/98 Runoff=0.09 cfs 1,359 cf
Subcatchment B2: BASIN 2	Runoff Area=0.729 ac 65.00% Impervious Runoff Depth=1.62" Tc=15.0 min CN=61/98 Runoff=0.25 cfs 4,286 cf
Subcatchment B3: BASIN 3	Runoff Area=0.371 ac 65.00% Impervious Runoff Depth=1.62" Tc=15.0 min CN=61/98 Runoff=0.13 cfs 2,181 cf
Subcatchment B4: BASIN-4	Runoff Area=0.383 ac 65.00% Impervious Runoff Depth=1.62" Tc=15.0 min CN=61/98 Runoff=0.13 cfs 2,252 cf
Subcatchment B5: BASIN-5	Runoff Area=0.802 ac 65.00% Impervious Runoff Depth=1.62" Tc=10.0 min CN=61/98 Runoff=0.30 cfs 4,716 cf
Subcatchment B6: BASIN-6	Runoff Area=0.072 ac 65.00% Impervious Runoff Depth=1.62" Tc=15.0 min CN=61/98 Runoff=0.02 cfs 423 cf
Reach ST-1: STORM PIPE-1	Avg. Flow Depth=0.00' Max Vel=0.00 fps 12.0" Round Pipe n=0.013 L=31.0' S=0.0935 '/' Capacity=10.90 cfs Outflow=0.00 cfs 0 cf
Reach ST-3: STORM PIPE-3	Avg. Flow Depth=0.09' Max Vel=2.64 fps Inflow=0.09 cfs 1,359 cf 12.0" Round Pipe n=0.012 L=21.0' S=0.0210 '/' Capacity=5.59 cfs Outflow=0.09 cfs 1,359 cf
Reach ST-5: STORM PIPE-5	Avg. Flow Depth=0.18' Max Vel=3.67 fps Inflow=0.34 cfs 5,646 cf 12.0" Round Pipe n=0.013 L=65.0' S=0.0202 '/' Capacity=5.06 cfs Outflow=0.34 cfs 5,646 cf
Reach ST-6: STORM PIPE-6	Avg. Flow Depth=0.20' Max Vel=4.08 fps Inflow=0.47 cfs 7,827 cf 12.0" Round Pipe n=0.013 L=20.0' S=0.0210 '/' Capacity=5.16 cfs Outflow=0.47 cfs 7,827 cf
Reach ST-7: STORM PIPE 7	Avg. Flow Depth=0.28' Max Vel=3.37 fps Inflow=0.60 cfs 10,079 cf 12.0" Round Pipe n=0.013 L=64.0' S=0.0100 '/' Capacity=3.56 cfs Outflow=0.60 cfs 10,079 cf
Reach ST-8: STORM PIPE-8	Avg. Flow Depth=0.14' Max Vel=4.67 fps Inflow=0.30 cfs 4,716 cf 12.0" Round Pipe n=0.013 L=93.0' S=0.0451 '/' Capacity=7.56 cfs Outflow=0.30 cfs 4,716 cf
Reach ST-9: STORM PIPE-9	Avg. Flow Depth=0.25' Max Vel=5.80 fps Inflow=0.89 cfs 14,795 cf 12.0" Round Pipe n=0.013 L=80.0' S=0.0331 '/' Capacity=6.48 cfs Outflow=0.89 cfs 14,795 cf
Pond PA: POND A	Peak Elev=3.95' Storage=2,831 cf Inflow=0.92 cfs 15,218 cf Outflow=0.32 cfs 15,229 cf

Total Runoff Area = 109,553 sf Runoff Volume = 15,218 cf Average Runoff Depth = 1.67"
32.80% Pervious = 35,935 sf 67.20% Impervious = 73,619 sf

Summary for Subcatchment B1: BASIN 1

[49] Hint: $T_c < 2dt$ may require smaller dt

Runoff = 0.09 cfs @ 7.98 hrs, Volume= 1,359 cf, Depth= 2.37"

Runoff by SBUH method, Split Pervious/Imperv., Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
 Type IA 24-hr 100-Year Rainfall=2.60"

Area (ac)	CN	Description	Land Use
0.158	98	Paved parking, HSG B	Pavement
0.158		100.00% Impervious Area	

Tc (min)	Length (feet)	Slope (ft/ft)	Velocity (ft/sec)	Capacity (cfs)	Description
10.0					Direct Entry,

Subcatchment B1: BASIN 1

Hydrograph

Summary for Subcatchment B2: BASIN 2

Runoff = 0.25 cfs @ 8.01 hrs, Volume= 4,286 cf, Depth= 1.62"

Runoff by SBUH method, Split Pervious/Imperv., Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
 Type IA 24-hr 100-Year Rainfall=2.60"

Area (ac)	CN	Description	Land Use
0.729	85	1/8 acre lots, 65% imp, HSG B	Pavement
0.255		35.00% Pervious Area	
0.474		65.00% Impervious Area	

Tc (min)	Length (feet)	Slope (ft/ft)	Velocity (ft/sec)	Capacity (cfs)	Description
15.0					Direct Entry,

Subcatchment B2: BASIN 2

Hydrograph

Summary for Subcatchment B3: BASIN 3

Runoff = 0.13 cfs @ 8.01 hrs, Volume= 2,181 cf, Depth= 1.62"

Runoff by SBUH method, Split Pervious/Imperv., Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
 Type IA 24-hr 100-Year Rainfall=2.60"

Area (ac)	CN	Description	Land Use
0.371	85	1/8 acre lots, 65% imp, HSG B	Residential
0.130		35.00% Pervious Area	
0.241		65.00% Impervious Area	

Tc (min)	Length (feet)	Slope (ft/ft)	Velocity (ft/sec)	Capacity (cfs)	Description
15.0					Direct Entry,

Subcatchment B3: BASIN 3

Hydrograph

Summary for Subcatchment B4: BASIN-4

Runoff = 0.13 cfs @ 8.01 hrs, Volume= 2,252 cf, Depth= 1.62"

Runoff by SBUH method, Split Pervious/Imperv., Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
 Type IA 24-hr 100-Year Rainfall=2.60"

Area (ac)	CN	Description	Land Use
0.383	85	1/8 acre lots, 65% imp, HSG B	Residential
0.134		35.00% Pervious Area	
0.249		65.00% Impervious Area	

Tc (min)	Length (feet)	Slope (ft/ft)	Velocity (ft/sec)	Capacity (cfs)	Description
15.0					Direct Entry,

Subcatchment B4: BASIN-4

Hydrograph

Summary for Subcatchment B5: BASIN-5

[49] Hint: Tc<2dt may require smaller dt

Runoff = 0.30 cfs @ 7.98 hrs, Volume= 4,716 cf, Depth= 1.62"

Runoff by SBUH method, Split Pervious/Imperv., Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
 Type IA 24-hr 100-Year Rainfall=2.60"

Area (ac)	CN	Description	Land Use
0.802	85	1/8 acre lots, 65% imp, HSG B	Residential
0.281		35.00% Pervious Area	
0.521		65.00% Impervious Area	

Tc (min)	Length (feet)	Slope (ft/ft)	Velocity (ft/sec)	Capacity (cfs)	Description
10.0					Direct Entry,

Subcatchment B5: BASIN-5

Hydrograph

Summary for Subcatchment B6: BASIN-6

Runoff = 0.02 cfs @ 8.01 hrs, Volume= 423 cf, Depth= 1.62"

Runoff by SBUH method, Split Pervious/Imperv., Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
 Type IA 24-hr 100-Year Rainfall=2.60"

Area (ac)	CN	Description	Land Use
0.072	85	1/8 acre lots, 65% imp, HSG B	Open Space
0.025		35.00% Pervious Area	
0.047		65.00% Impervious Area	

Tc (min)	Length (feet)	Slope (ft/ft)	Velocity (ft/sec)	Capacity (cfs)	Description
15.0					Direct Entry,

Subcatchment B6: BASIN-6

Hydrograph

Summary for Reach ST-1: STORM PIPE-1

[43] Hint: Has no inflow (Outflow=Zero)

Bank-Full Depth= 1.00' Flow Area= 0.8 sf, Capacity= 10.90 cfs

12.0" Round Pipe
 n= 0.013 Corrugated PE, smooth interior
 Length= 31.0' Slope= 0.0935 '/'
 Inlet Invert= 1,008.20', Outlet Invert= 1,005.30'

Reach ST-1: STORM PIPE-1

Hydrograph

Summary for Reach ST-3: STORM PIPE-3

[52] Hint: Inlet/Outlet conditions not evaluated

[61] Hint: Exceeded Reach ST-1 outlet invert by 0.09' @ 8.00 hrs

Inflow Area = 6,882 sf, 100.00% Impervious, Inflow Depth = 2.37" for 100-Year event
Inflow = 0.09 cfs @ 7.98 hrs, Volume= 1,359 cf
Outflow = 0.09 cfs @ 7.98 hrs, Volume= 1,359 cf, Atten= 0%, Lag= 0.1 min

Routing by Dyn-Stor-Ind method, Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
Max. Velocity= 2.64 fps, Min. Travel Time= 0.1 min
Avg. Velocity = 1.49 fps, Avg. Travel Time= 0.2 min

Peak Storage= 1 cf @ 7.98 hrs
Average Depth at Peak Storage= 0.09'
Bank-Full Depth= 1.00' Flow Area= 0.8 sf, Capacity= 5.59 cfs

12.0" Round Pipe
n= 0.012 Corrugated PP, smooth interior
Length= 21.0' Slope= 0.0210 '/'
Inlet Invert= 1,005.30', Outlet Invert= 1,004.86'

Reach ST-3: STORM PIPE-3

Hydrograph

Summary for Reach ST-5: STORM PIPE-5

[52] Hint: Inlet/Outlet conditions not evaluated

Inflow Area = 38,638 sf, 71.23% Impervious, Inflow Depth = 1.75" for 100-Year event
 Inflow = 0.34 cfs @ 8.00 hrs, Volume= 5,646 cf
 Outflow = 0.34 cfs @ 8.01 hrs, Volume= 5,646 cf, Atten= 0%, Lag= 0.2 min

Routing by Dyn-Stor-Ind method, Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
 Max. Velocity= 3.67 fps, Min. Travel Time= 0.3 min
 Avg. Velocity = 2.08 fps, Avg. Travel Time= 0.5 min

Peak Storage= 6 cf @ 8.01 hrs
 Average Depth at Peak Storage= 0.18'
 Bank-Full Depth= 1.00' Flow Area= 0.8 sf, Capacity= 5.06 cfs

12.0" Round Pipe
 n= 0.013 Corrugated PE, smooth interior
 Length= 65.0' Slope= 0.0202 '/'
 Inlet Invert= 996.79', Outlet Invert= 995.48'

Reach ST-5: STORM PIPE-5

Hydrograph

Summary for Reach ST-6: STORM PIPE-6

[52] Hint: Inlet/Outlet conditions not evaluated

[61] Hint: Exceeded Reach ST-5 outlet invert by 0.10' @ 8.00 hrs

Inflow Area = 54,798 sf, 69.40% Impervious, Inflow Depth = 1.71" for 100-Year event
Inflow = 0.47 cfs @ 8.01 hrs, Volume= 7,827 cf
Outflow = 0.47 cfs @ 8.01 hrs, Volume= 7,827 cf, Atten= 0%, Lag= 0.1 min

Routing by Dyn-Stor-Ind method, Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
Max. Velocity= 4.08 fps, Min. Travel Time= 0.1 min
Avg. Velocity = 2.33 fps, Avg. Travel Time= 0.1 min

Peak Storage= 2 cf @ 8.01 hrs
Average Depth at Peak Storage= 0.20'
Bank-Full Depth= 1.00' Flow Area= 0.8 sf, Capacity= 5.16 cfs

12.0" Round Pipe
n= 0.013 Corrugated PE, smooth interior
Length= 20.0' Slope= 0.0210 '/'
Inlet Invert= 995.38', Outlet Invert= 994.96'

Reach ST-6: STORM PIPE-6

Hydrograph

Summary for Reach ST-7: STORM PIPE 7

[52] Hint: Inlet/Outlet conditions not evaluated

[61] Hint: Exceeded Reach ST-6 outlet invert by 0.18' @ 8.00 hrs

Inflow Area = 71,482 sf, 68.37% Impervious, Inflow Depth = 1.69" for 100-Year event
Inflow = 0.60 cfs @ 8.01 hrs, Volume= 10,079 cf
Outflow = 0.60 cfs @ 8.01 hrs, Volume= 10,079 cf, Atten= 0%, Lag= 0.2 min

Routing by Dyn-Stor-Ind method, Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
Max. Velocity= 3.37 fps, Min. Travel Time= 0.3 min
Avg. Velocity = 1.92 fps, Avg. Travel Time= 0.6 min

Peak Storage= 11 cf @ 8.01 hrs
Average Depth at Peak Storage= 0.28'
Bank-Full Depth= 1.00' Flow Area= 0.8 sf, Capacity= 3.56 cfs

12.0" Round Pipe
n= 0.013 Corrugated PE, smooth interior
Length= 64.0' Slope= 0.0100 '/'
Inlet Invert= 994.86', Outlet Invert= 994.22'

Reach ST-7: STORM PIPE 7

Hydrograph

Summary for Reach ST-8: STORM PIPE-8

[52] Hint: Inlet/Outlet conditions not evaluated

Inflow Area = 34,935 sf, 65.00% Impervious, Inflow Depth = 1.62" for 100-Year event
 Inflow = 0.30 cfs @ 7.98 hrs, Volume= 4,716 cf
 Outflow = 0.30 cfs @ 7.98 hrs, Volume= 4,716 cf, Atten= 0%, Lag= 0.2 min

Routing by Dyn-Stor-Ind method, Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
 Max. Velocity= 4.67 fps, Min. Travel Time= 0.3 min
 Avg. Velocity = 2.66 fps, Avg. Travel Time= 0.6 min

Peak Storage= 6 cf @ 7.98 hrs
 Average Depth at Peak Storage= 0.14'
 Bank-Full Depth= 1.00' Flow Area= 0.8 sf, Capacity= 7.56 cfs

12.0" Round Pipe
 n= 0.013 Corrugated PE, smooth interior
 Length= 93.0' Slope= 0.0451 '/'
 Inlet Invert= 997.94', Outlet Invert= 993.75'

Reach ST-8: STORM PIPE-8

Hydrograph

Summary for Reach ST-9: STORM PIPE-9

[52] Hint: Inlet/Outlet conditions not evaluated

[62] Hint: Exceeded Reach ST-8 OUTLET depth by 0.02' @ 8.00 hrs

Inflow Area = 106,417 sf, 67.26% Impervious, Inflow Depth = 1.67" for 100-Year event
Inflow = 0.89 cfs @ 8.00 hrs, Volume= 14,795 cf
Outflow = 0.89 cfs @ 8.00 hrs, Volume= 14,795 cf, Atten= 0%, Lag= 0.2 min

Routing by Dyn-Stor-Ind method, Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
Max. Velocity= 5.80 fps, Min. Travel Time= 0.2 min
Avg. Velocity = 3.28 fps, Avg. Travel Time= 0.4 min

Peak Storage= 12 cf @ 8.00 hrs
Average Depth at Peak Storage= 0.25'
Bank-Full Depth= 1.00' Flow Area= 0.8 sf, Capacity= 6.48 cfs

12.0" Round Pipe
n= 0.013 Corrugated PE, smooth interior
Length= 80.0' Slope= 0.0331 '/
Inlet Invert= 993.65', Outlet Invert= 991.00'

Reach ST-9: STORM PIPE-9

Summary for Pond PA: POND A

Inflow Area = 109,553 sf, 67.20% Impervious, Inflow Depth = 1.67" for 100-Year event
 Inflow = 0.92 cfs @ 8.00 hrs, Volume= 15,218 cf
 Outflow = 0.32 cfs @ 9.20 hrs, Volume= 15,229 cf, Atten= 65%, Lag= 71.7 min
 Discarded = 0.32 cfs @ 9.20 hrs, Volume= 15,229 cf

Routing by Dyn-Stor-Ind method, Time Span= 0.00-36.00 hrs, dt= 0.10 hrs
 Peak Elev= 3.95' @ 9.20 hrs Surf.Area= 1,175 sf Storage= 2,831 cf

Plug-Flow detention time= 96.0 min calculated for 15,187 cf (100% of inflow)
 Center-of-Mass det. time= 96.3 min (795.7 - 699.4)

Volume	Invert	Avail.Storage	Storage Description
#1	0.00'	4,217 cf	17.00'W x 20.00'L x 5.00'H Prismatic Z=2.0

Device	Routing	Invert	Outlet Devices
#1	Discarded	0.00'	10.800 in/hr Exfiltration over Wetted area

Discarded OutFlow Max=0.32 cfs @ 9.20 hrs HW=3.95' (Free Discharge)
 ↳1=Exfiltration (Exfiltration Controls 0.32 cfs)

Pond PA: POND A

Hydrograph

